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Teachers' Information Communication Technology (ICT) Competence as a Mediator of Technology Integration and Students' Academic Performance in Secondary Schools in Rivers State, Nigeria

¹Dr. Igbozuruike, Innocent U.; ²Dr. Mba, Calistus O. & ³Usman Haruna

^{1,2}Department of Educational Management,
Faculty of Education,
University of Port Harcourt, Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria.

³Department of Educational Foundations,
Faculty of Education,
Prince Abubakar Audu University Anyigba, Kogi State, Nigeria

ABSTRACT

This study investigated the mediating role of Teachers' Information Communication Technology (ICT) Competence in the relationship between Technology Integration and Students' Academic Performance in Secondary Schools in Rivers State. Two research questions and seven hypotheses guided the study. This study adopted a correlational survey design. The population of the study was 7,186 teachers serving in public secondary schools in Rivers State. The data used in this study were collected from a sample of 329 teachers selected through the stratified random sampling technique. A structured questionnaire developed from validated empirical instruments and literature, was used to obtain measurement data for the five latent constructs in the study, namely, instructional delivery, assessment, record-keeping, teacher ICT competence, and academic performance. Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) was conducted using LISREL 8.8 to examine both the measurement and structural models. The model demonstrated adequate reliability and validity with acceptable fit indices ($\chi^2/df = 2.45$, CFI = 0.90, RMSEA = 0.08, NFI = 0.90, GFI = 0.89, AGFI = 0.88). The results showed that technology-supported instructional delivery and record-keeping significantly predicted both teacher ICT competence and students' academic performance. Assessment significantly influenced students' academic performance directly but showed no significant effect on teacher ICT competence. Furthermore, teacher ICT competence partially mediated the effects of instructional delivery and record-keeping on students' academic performance, while no mediating effect was observed between assessment and students' academic performance. These findings underscore the differentiated pathways through which technology integration enhances learning outcomes. This study recommends that the government should invest in school digital infrastructure, sustain teacher professional development initiatives, and implement curriculum reforms that embed ICT competencies across all levels of instruction. In addition, school managers should reinforce institutional support systems

to ensure that the availability of digital technologies translates into effective pedagogical application in the classroom.

Keywords: Information Communication Technology (ICT), Teachers' Competence, Mediator, Technology Integration, Students, Academic Performance, Secondary Schools, Rivers State, Nigeria.

INTRODUCTION

The integration of modern educational technologies into daily school instructional practices has become increasingly central to the on-going discussions on how to improve students' academic performance in a sustainable manner. Modern educational technologies are diverse and multifaceted in their uses. They include mobile applications, multimedia platforms, virtual learning environments, cloud-based services, AI-powered tutoring systems, augmented and virtual reality tools, gamified learning platforms, and learning analytics systems. These innovations have become key facilitators of knowledge transfer and effective enablers of pedagogical practices. Pedagogical practices refer to the instructional activities and professional responsibilities through which teachers apply educational principles, methods, and guidelines to achieve educational objectives. These practices encompass lesson planning, instructional delivery, record-keeping, student assessment, and the integration of learning resources (Alexander, 2008; Voyer et al., 2014).

The degree to which educators adopt and integrate learning resources such as digital tools into their daily functions in areas of instructional delivery, student assessment, and record-keeping can influence the development of teachers' ICT competence and their responsiveness to digital pedagogy (UNESCO, 2023; Ukaigwe & Igbozuruike, 2019; Monserate, 2018). Digital instructional delivery is the use of technological tools and platforms to communicate subject matter in a way that engages the learner, strengthens their understanding and enriches their learning experiences. When these tools are skilfully utilized, they can enhance the quality and reach of instruction. In addition to enabling teachers to adapt instructional content to meet diverse learning needs, the tools can also be adjusted to suit specific learning preference, making them versatile and highly customisable. Adesope and Ezinne (2018) observed that devices such as interactive whiteboards and digital cameras can significantly improve the effectiveness of classroom instruction. The researchers remarked that ICTs promote active teacher-led student engagement in classroom, adding that such experiential learning process has an increased likelihood of strengthening learner's skills acquisition and knowledge retention (Adesope & Ezinne, 2018).

Social and collaborative technologies such as Facebook, YouTube, Skype, and Microsoft Office have demonstrated considerable usefulness as learning mediums and enablers. When these platforms are effectively integrated into the conventional school-based teaching methods to support real-time interactions and classroom engagement, their effects on learning have been shown to be substantial. For instance, Li and Wang (2023), Wang and Lu (2024) and Fan et al. (2023) found that social media tools enhanced student engagement, boosted learning self-efficacy, and supported teacher professional development initiatives. Corroborating this, Monserate (2018) reported that in classrooms where technology was purposefully integrated, there was a notable improvement in teaching effectiveness, indicating that digital tools can significantly enhance students' learning experiences. This linear relationship has been linked to the ability of some of these to create and stimulate interactive and dynamic learning environments where students can engage in hands-on learning exercises.

Despite the acknowledged benefits associated with modern technology, its integration into instructional delivery has continued to face significant challenges. In many Less Developed Countries (LDCs), including Nigeria, teachers tend to utilise modern technology at a minimal level, resulting in limited improvement in their ICT competence and little to no meaningful impact on students' academic performance (Aregbesola & Adeleke, 2021). Gause et al. (2022) identified some of the major barriers to teacher technology utilisation as inadequate technological infrastructure, insufficient teacher training on technology use, and varying levels of digital competence. These challenges have been identified by several scholars as leading causes of inefficiencies and inconsistencies in curriculum implementation

(Ikwuka et al., 2021; Burns & Santally, 2019, November). They have also been reported as major contributing factors to poor academic performance among students (Chai et al., 2022; Chiukpai et al., 2023).

While examining the inconsistencies between policy expectations and actual classroom practices, Abedi (2023) observed that educational policies have frequently advocated for student-centred and constructivist learning approaches, which involve the practical use of technology in classroom settings; however, the teachers on their part have continued largely to use technology in ways that do not indicate their willingness to embrace a change in instructional pedagogy, as their teaching methods and classroom behaviours have predominantly tended towards using instructional technologies to support the traditional teacher-centred method. This discrepancy between policy direction and actual teacher-classroom practices indicates either the insufficiency of policy framework or the poor implementation of it to promote teacher-led technology use in the classroom.

In addition to instructional delivery, these tools also make it possible for teachers to conduct assessments, and continuously monitor students' academic progress, obtain instant feedback from learners, and conduct performance analytics, all of which are essential parts of data-informed instruction. Formative assessment technologies such as in-person classrooms questioning, and online quizzes, e-portfolios and interactive response systems can help teachers to identify learning gaps among students, inform future instructions and support continuous improvement in instructional delivery. In parallel, summative evaluation tools such as computer-based tests and digital rubrics are designed to offer structured and standardised systems-based evaluation to determine students' cumulative learning outcomes. The extent to which teachers use these tools effectively, flexibly and responsively has a strong bearing on their performance efficiency.

These tools can enable teachers to easily generate meaningful insights on student learning progress, support differentiated instruction, and enhance students' engagement in the learning process. Information obtained from assessment can empower teachers to tailor responsive feedback to underachieving students, which may be in the form of adjusting instructional design and delivery strategies to meet identified needs. In alignment with this viewpoint, Nwonkwo and Ogwunte (2024) argued that teachers who are proficient in the use of digital assessment platforms are more likely to provide appropriate instructional response that could make a difference in contributing to students' academic performance. This perspective supports one of the assumptions of this study – that teachers' engagement with well-structured technology-driven assessment practices can promote the development of ICT competence among such teachers, especially when those practices are built into the operational fabric of the classroom.

In spite of these strengths, Ventouris et al. (2021) observed that excessive reliance on digital assessments might lead to unintended neglect of essential cognitive skills measures, including critical thinking and analytical reasoning, as some of the digital test tools are notoriously known for measuring mainly rote memorisation or basic comprehension. The scholars therefore cautioned that if digital assessments are not properly designed and carefully embedded with broader standardised assessment rubrics, they could lead to heightened concentration on measurement of superficial learning experiences, instead of deeper cognitive engagement and evaluation among learners. Ukaigwe and Igbozuruike (2019) supported this cautionary perspective, having stated that a successful integration of a digital assessment approach into the school ecosystem requires two basic things; a systematic capacity-building programmes aimed at strengthening teachers' technical competencies, and two, a deliberate support from school leadership and systems-based backing that strongly encourages pedagogical shifts away from teacher-centred to learner-centric instructional approaches.

Record-keeping is an essential part of teachers' function. This function has evolved over time, transitioning from traditional manual filing systems to robust digital platforms and tools that teachers now use to enhance data storage, accuracy, ease of access, and security. Digital record-keeping systems such as Google Classroom, interactive whiteboards, Zoom, voice recording apps, and attendance tracking applications are designed with useful features that help teachers to record and manage critical aspects of student information and activities, including class attendance, academic performance trends, and

behavioural records, in an integrated and user-friendly format (Yadav & Chakraborty, 2021; Usman & Igbozuruike, 2017). As educational institutions seek to streamline administrative operations, these record-keeping tools have become vital for tracking student progress and informing decision-making. Awaji and Solaiman (2022) observed that blockchain-based systems in educational record management have demonstrated a strong capacity to safeguard the authenticity and integrity of students' academic records, and with similar efficiency in facilitating seamless data validation and information verification tasks. These capabilities underscore how technological advancements are increasingly redefining not only how classroom instruction can be conducted, but also how digital tools embedded in administrative functions can support the development of ICT competence among teachers, and raise students' academic performance thereby. Nwonkwo and Ogwunte (2024) said that when school structures promote the adoption of electronic systems, teachers will gradually build the capacity to manage attendance records, track academic performance, and facilitate transparent communication with stakeholders. The resulting improvements in teachers' administrative efficiency can enhance the quality of educational service delivery and strengthen the organisational structures' capacity to respond more effectively to students' academic and welfare needs.

Given the multidimensional nature of educational technology utilisation, measuring its effects on students' academic performance becomes essential for deepening our understanding of its impact. Some researchers have consistently pointed out that the effectiveness of educational technologies cannot be measured in isolation from the specific contexts and conditions in which they are applied. A study by Batdi *et al.* (2018) revealed that technology-supported teaching had a positive effect on students' academic achievement, although the extent of the said impact was varied and depended largely on contextual factors such as the type of technology used, the implementation strategy, and the subject teaching matter involved. Similarly, Monserate (2018) reported a positive and significant correlation between the use of technology in teaching and students' academic performance. The strength of this correlation was reportedly stronger in schools with adequate infrastructure, proper teacher training, and strong administrative support systems, which collectively serve as key predictors of effective integration of technology into instructional delivery and administrative processes, leading to teachers' capacity-building in ICT competence.

Ventouris *et al.* (2021) noted that the impact of teacher-technology use extends beyond academic metrics. They further argued that its influence on learners' emotional and behavioural development is also significant, highlighting the need for teachers to consistently guide students on how to use technology properly to maintain balance in their digital interactions and healthy mindset conducive to learning. The situation within the Nigerian educational context mirrors the complex global narrative regarding educational technology integration. In recent years, educational policymakers have demonstrated a growing awareness of the transformative promise embedded in utilization of digital tools in the classroom, leading to increased advocacy for and investments in ICT infrastructural provision and targeted teacher retraining programmes to improve teaching quality and students' academic performance (Nwonkwo & Ogwunte, 2024). However, the actual translation of these investments into meaningful classroom practices remains uneven. Ukaigwe and Igbozuruike (2019) attributed this situation as stemming from the government's penchant for issuing educational directives that promote the use of sophisticated instructional technologies and learner-centred pedagogies without making corresponding investments in teacher preparation to empower them to use these tools effectively – a situation that has often resulted in teachers continuing with, or reverting to the conventional teaching methods.

The effectiveness of technological deployment in education is largely contingent upon the competence and confidence of the teachers implementing it (Nwonkwo & Ogwunte, 2024; Chiukpai *et al.*, 2023; Ikwuka *et al.*, 2021). In this context, competence refers to the teacher's ability to integrate a combination of knowledge, technical skills, and professional confidence necessary for the successful adoption, application, and management of educational technologies in performing instructional duties (Ukaigwe & Igbozuruike, 2020). Where such competence is lacking, technological resources are often underutilised or

misapplied, and this may encourage unsatisfactory educational outcomes. Gause et al. (2022) emphasised that effective technology integration in education demands a focus on equity in resource distribution and capacity building. The researchers cautioned that inadequate teacher competencies can lead to inconsistent use of technology and may contribute in widening the gap in educational disparities. In addition to human capacity challenges, infrastructural inadequacies and unequal distribution of resources also pose obstacles to technology adoption in state schools. Burns and Santally (2019, November) observed that unreliable electricity supply, limited internet connectivity, and inadequate data security constitute critical barriers that undermine teachers' capacity to utilise technology effectively.

The alignment between technology-driven educational policy objectives and actual classroom practices is a fundamental determinant of successful technology integration Ventouris et al. (2021) said that active collaboration between teachers and parents are crucial in curriculum implementation. The researchers argued that teachers alone cannot achieve optimal technology integration without robust support from parents and guardians. Consequently, developing strong partnerships between schools, teachers, and families has become a vital pathway to creating coherent and consistent technological environments at home and at school. Such a partnership can enhance the effectiveness of technology integration initiatives and reinforce the responsible use of digital tools among students, who might otherwise misuse them (Igbozuruike & Usman, 2019).

Given the complexities identified in previous studies, the present investigation examined how teachers utilise modern educational technologies in key areas of instructional delivery, student assessment, and administrative record-keeping, as well as how these applications influence students' academic performance in secondary schools in Rivers State. The study further explored Teacher ICT Competence as a mediating construct, and sought to determine the extent to which it transmits the effects of school-level practices to students' academic outcomes. The conceptual framework of this study was guided by our understanding and supposition that performance of core pedagogical practices with the aid of technologies on the part of teachers in the areas of instructional delivery, assessment, and record-keeping, can either support or constrain the development of teachers' ICT competencies, which in turn influence both their instructional effectiveness and students' academic performance.

Statement of the Problem

In recent years, educational authorities and institutions have increasingly prioritised the integration of modern educational technologies as a means of improving the quality of teaching, learning, and school management. However, despite the proliferation of digital tools and policies supporting their use, the expected improvements in students' academic performance and overall service delivery in many schools has remained largely unmet. A major challenge observed in this regard lies in the manner and extent to which teachers utilise these technologies in the performance of their core pedagogical practices. In some schools, certain instructional technologies are available, while in others, the availability varies in degrees, yet their integration into classroom instruction, performance assessment processes, and administrative activities is often shallow, inconsistent in application, and often poorly aligned with pedagogical best practices.

This underutilisation raises serious concerns and portends severe implications on students' educational outcomes. When teachers lack the requisite skills or confidence to effectively apply technological tools in instructional delivery, students are automatically deprived of active engagement in the learning process, as interactivity and differentiated learning experiences would be adversely affected. Similarly, when technological tools are not effectively used by teachers in assessing students, timely feedback and data-driven instructional adjustments could become difficult, and this is capable of exacerbating academic performance issues among learners. More importantly, the traditional paperwork-based record-keeping is inefficient; it compromises transparency, increases delay in important student-related interventions, communication, and administrative responsiveness. If this problem remains unaddressed, it threatens to widen performance disparities and increases inefficiencies across the state schools, and this could further erode the value of public investment in educational technology, thereby hindering the development of a

competitive 21st-century-ready student population. As part of addressing these challenges, this study examined how teachers’ utilisation of modern educational technologies translates into meaningful improvements in teaching effectiveness and student achievement in secondary schools in Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study.

1. To what extent does teacher ICT competence mediate the relationship between technology integration in core pedagogical practices (instruction, assessment, and record-keeping) and students' academic performance in secondary schools in Rivers State?.
2. What is the effect of technology integration in core pedagogical practices (instruction, assessment, and record-keeping) on the academic performance of students in secondary schools in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested in the study.

- H1:** Technology integration in assessment has a significant effect on teacher ICT competence in secondary schools in Rivers State.
- H2:** Technology integration in instructional delivery has a significant effect on teacher ICT competence in secondary schools in Rivers State.
- H3:** Technology integration in record-keeping has a significant effect on teacher ICT competence in secondary schools in Rivers State.
- H4:** Teacher ICT competence has a significant effect on students' academic performance in secondary schools in Rivers State.
- H5:** Technology integration in assessment has a significant effect on students’ academic performance in secondary schools in Rivers State.
- H6:** Technology integration in instructional delivery has a significant effect on students’ academic performance in secondary schools in Rivers State.
- H7:** Technology integration in record-keeping has a significant effect on students’ academic performance in secondary schools in Rivers State.

Figure 1: Research Model

Note: All hypothesized relationships are positive, except H1

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a correlational survey design. The design is appropriate for examining associative and predictive relationships among latent variables. Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) was implemented in this study using LISREL 8.8 to evaluate both the measurement and structural models, involving the independent variables namely, Instructional Delivery (ID) Assessment (A) and Record-Keeping (RK). The mediator variable is Teacher ICT Competence (TIC), while the outcome variable is students' Academic Performance (AP). The model conceptualises technology-based instructional, assessment, and record-keeping practices as channels through which teachers utilise ICT tools to enhance their job performance and students' achievement.

Population and Sampling Technique

The target population comprised 7,186 teachers across 291 public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. A sample size of 384 teachers was selected for the study. A stratified random sampling technique was adopted to ensure fair representation of teachers across geographical and infrastructural variations in the state. From 12 randomly selected LGAs out of the 23 LGAs in the state, four schools were chosen per LGA, and eight teachers were randomly drawn from each of the schools, resulting in a total sample size of 384 teachers. This sample size exceeds Kline's (2016) minimum threshold for SEM, and was sufficient for statistical power and parameter estimation. The sample determination was conducted using Taro Yamane's formula: $n = N / (1 + N \times e^2)$. Substituting, $n = 7186 / (1 + 7186 \times 0.0025) = 7186 / 18.965 \approx 379$. An additional five (5) teachers were added to enhance sample representativeness and to account for possible non-responses or incomplete data entries, as advised by Israel (1992). This brought the total sample size to 384.

Instrument for Data Collection

A structured questionnaire developed by the researchers from existing validated scales and empirical literature was used to measure the five latent constructs estimated. It comprised six sections: Section one was used to obtain demographic data of the respondents, and five others contained items corresponding to Instructional Delivery (ID), Assessment (A), Record-Keeping (RK), Teacher ICT Competence (TIC), and Academic Performance (AP). All responses were rated on a five-point Likert scale ranging from Strongly Disagree (1) to Strongly Agree (5). The indicators employed to measure the latent variables are presented in Table 1

Validity and Reliability of the instrument

Through expert reviews and validation processes, the questionnaire used to collect data was confirmed to be valid in terms of content and face validity. A pilot study was conducted with 30 teachers from schools outside the sampled 12 LGAs. Data obtained were used to perform internal consistency assessment using Cronbach's Alpha in SPSS. After removing a few items with outliers, the alpha coefficients for the five constructs yielded values of 0.84, 0.76, 0.81, 0.79, and 0.89, respectively for Instructional Delivery (ID), Assessment (A), Record-Keeping (RK), and Academic Performance (AP), indicating an acceptable level of internal consistency. These values met the reliability threshold of 0.70 recommended by Tabachnick and Fidell (2001). Of the 384 questionnaires distributed to the teachers at their various stations, only 329 responses were returned valid and used for analysis. The remaining 55 questionnaire copies (14.32%) were incompletely and improperly filled and considered invalid.

DATA ANALYSIS PROCEDURE

Structural Equation Modelling (SEM)

Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) and Path Analysis

Structural Equation Model (SEM) was used to explore the hypothesized relationships in the research model (see Figure 1). Exploratory factor analysis was performed to examine the factor loadings and validity of the observed constructs. This led to deletion of some items with cross-loading issue, along with those with λ values below 0.4. The observed constructs for each of the respective latent variables finally loaded successfully, with their values ranging from 0.41 to 0.97, and were considered acceptable

for exploratory research (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2001). Out of the six initial items used to measure each latent variable, four items loaded satisfactorily for Assessment (A), Instructional Delivery (ID), and Record Keeping (RK). For Teacher ICT Competence (TIC), three items showed adequate loadings, whereas four items loaded properly for Academic Performance (AP). To establish the discriminant and convergent validity of the constructs, a first-order Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) was conducted using LISREL 8.8. The results of this analysis are presented in Table 1 and illustrated in Figure 2 and Figure 3. Composite Reliability (CR) was further employed to assess the internal consistency of the constructs. To certify discriminant validity, the Fornell-Larcker matrix and the Heterotrait-Monotrait (HTMT) ratio were conducted, both of which confirmed the distinctiveness of the latent variables (see table 5 and 6). Harman’s single-factor test was also performed, and the result indicated that the first factor accounted for 34% of the total variance, which is below the 50% threshold, confirming thus that the influence of Common Method Bias (CMB) on the observed associations among latent variables was not substantial (Podsakoff et al., 2003).

Table 1: Model measurement and confirmatory factors analysis (endogenous and exogenous variables).

S/n	Measurement Item	λ	t-value	CR	AVE	Remarks
Assessment (A)				0.86	0.62	Valid/reliable
A1	I grade assignments using Excel.	0.43	7.69			
A2	I give feedback via comments on digital platforms.	0.72	14.99			
A3	I track students' progress electronically.	0.97	23.43			
A4	I assess students with auto-grading tools.	0.91	20.90			
Instructional Delivery (ID)				0.84	0.59	Valid/reliable
ID1	I use multimedia tools in teaching.	0.46	8.65			
ID2	I apply interactive apps in lessons.	0.59	11.49			
ID3	I deliver lessons with digital presentations.	0.96	22.98			
ID4	I explain concepts using digital whiteboards.	0.94	22.23			
Record-Keeping (RK)				0.81	0.54	Valid/reliable
RC1	I keep digital attendance records.	0.41	7.53			
RC2	I store students' test scores in digital databases.	0.58	11.18			
RC3	I prepare students' reports electronically.	0.91	20.29			
RC4	I update students' records in real time.	0.90	19.87			
Teachers ICT Competence (TIC)				0.77	0.53	Valid/reliable
TIC1	I am confident in my ability to use ICT tools.	0.60	N/A			
TIC2	I can troubleshoot basic ICT issues.	0.81	9.77			
TIC3	I integrate technology into instruction.	0.75	8.82			
Academic Performance (AP)				0.87	0.63	Valid/reliable
AP1	Students' test scores have improved.	0.65	N/A			
AP2	Students show more academic interest when ICT aids are used.	0.76	11.81			
AP3	Student pass rates have increased.	0.91	13.30			
AP4	Digital tools improved students' performance.	0.84	12.74			

Note(s): λ = factor-loading lambda; AVE = Average Variance Extracted; CR = Composite Reliability, NA = Not Available, Measurement Fit: Chi-square (χ^2) 895.53; DF = 366; (Parsimonious Fit= χ^2/df = 2.45), Comparative fit index (CFI) = .90; RMSEA 0.08; Normed Fit Index (NFI) = 0.90; NNFI = 0.89; Goodness of Fit Index (GFI) = 0.89; AGFI = 0.88.

The measurement model indices indicates that λ , AVE, and CR, are consistent with the validity and reliability thresholds proposed by Fornell and Larcker (1981), who recommended AVE > 0.50 and CR > 0.70. The model fit indices observed from the analysis output yielded indices as thus: χ^2/df = 2.45, CFI =

0.90, RMSEA = 0.08, NFI = 0.90, NNFI = 0.89, GFI = 0.89 and AGFI = 0.88. All the indices are within acceptable limits for structural equation models as supported by Kline (2016), Hair et al. (2019), and Schermelleh-Engel et al. (2003). These values showed that the model fit is adequate.

Figure 2: Confirmatory Factor and Path Analysis (Estimate) Indexes

Figure 3: Confirmatory Factor and Path Analysis (T-value) Indexes

Hypotheses Testing Summary

The Table 2 presents the results of test of hypotheses for the structural paths in the model, using standardised path coefficients and t-values. Paths with t-values greater than or equal to 1.96 were considered statistically significant at $p < .05$. Based on these criteria, the remark column indicates whether each hypothesis is significant or not significant.

Table 2: Summary of Hypotheses Test

Hypotheses	Full Path	β	T-value	Remark
H1	Assessment → Teacher ICT Competence	-0.031	-0.53	Not Significant
H2	Instructional Delivery → Teacher ICT Competence	0.58**	7.43	Significant
H3	Record-Keeping → Teacher ICT Competence	0.47**	6.81	Significant
H4	Teacher ICT Competence → Academic Performance	0.21**	2.38	Significant
H5	Assessment → Academic Performance	0.25**	4.38	Significant
H6	Instructional Delivery → Academic Performance	0.16**	2.07	Significant
H7	Record-Keeping → Academic Performance	0.20**	2.91	Significant

Note(s): Measurement fit: Chi-square (χ^2) 895.53; DF = 366; (Parsimonious Fit= $\chi^2/df = 2.45$), Comparative fit index (CFI) = .90; RMSEA 0.08; Normed Fit Index (NFI) = 0.90; NNFI = 0.89; Goodness of Fit Index (GFI) = 0.89; AGFI = 0.88. β = Standardised coefficient; Paths are significant at $p < .05$ if $t \geq 1.96$.

In Table 2, we tested the seven structural hypotheses (H1 to H7). In Hypothesis 1 (H1), it was hypothesised that technology-driven Assessment would positively influence Teacher ICT Competence. However, the path coefficient observed was negative and statistically insignificant ($\beta = -0.031$; $t = -0.53$), indicating that the hypothesised relationship was not supported within the structural model. In contrast, Hypothesis 2 (H2) examined the effect of using technology in Instructional Delivery on Teacher ICT Competence. The result revealed a strong, positive, and statistically significant effect ($\beta = 0.58$; $t = 7.43$). This result suggests that improvements in instructional delivery through the use of technology can substantially enhance teachers' ICT competence. In H3, the hypothesis that technology-driven Record-Keeping exerts a positive effect on Teachers' ICT Competence was supported, with a significant path coefficient ($\beta = 0.47$; $t = 6.81$, > 1.96). This implies that digital documentation of students' records as part of teachers' classroom-based pedagogical practices play a vital role in increasing teacher's readiness to use technology in classroom context. Hypothesis 4 (H4) purports that Teacher ICT Competence exerts influence on students' academic performance. The path analysis yielded a positive and statistically significant path coefficient ($\beta = 0.21$; $t = 2.38$, > 1.96). This confirms that a higher level of ICT competence among teachers is associated with improved students' academic performance. Hypothesis 5 (H5) proposed a direct relationship between technology-driven Assessment practices and Academic Performance. The model supported this hypothesis with a statistically significant result ($\beta = 0.25$; $t = 4.38$, > 1.96), indicating strongly that technology-driven assessment practices by teachers exert a substantial influence on students' academic achievement. Similarly, Hypothesis 6 (H6) tested the effect of technology-driven Instructional Delivery on students' Academic Performance. This relationship was also confirmed as significant ($\beta = 0.16$; $t = 2.07$, > 1.96), implying thus that, a technology-enabled instruction delivery exerts a positive and significant effect on students' academic performance.

Hypothesis 7 (H7) assessed the link between technology-supported Record-Keeping and students' Academic Performance. The analysis produced a statistically significant result ($\beta = 0.20$; $t = 2.91$, > 1.96), reinforcing the role of technology in enhancing administrative documentation, and students' academic outcomes. Collectively, the results demonstrate that Teacher ICT Competence mediates the relationships between technology-led Instructional Delivery and Academic Performance, as well as between technology-led Record-Keeping and Academic Performance. However, no mediating effect was observed in the relationship between technology-driven assessment practices and students' academic performance. One possible reason for this non-significant mediating effect may be the limited utilisation of digital tools

in classroom assessment processes. This could stem from several underlying factors, such as inadequate teacher training on digital assessment platforms, lack of access to reliable technological infrastructure, or institutional emphasis on traditional, paper-based evaluation systems. These constraints may have prevented teachers from fully integrating technology into assessment tasks in ways that could meaningfully influence students' learning outcomes. However, a substantial effect was observed between technology-driven Assessment practices and students' Academic Performance. These findings underscore the relevance of deploying modern technologies in instructional and teacher-led administrative practices to enhance teachers' ICT competence, which in turn contributes to improved academic outcomes among students.

Table 3: Correlation Matrix

	TIC	AP	ID	RK	A
AP	0.499*				
ID	0.333*	0.488*			
RK	0.510**	0.447*	0.330*		
A	0.616**	0.547**	0.487*	0.395*	
Mean	4.45	4.50	4.27	4.34	4.40
S.D.	0.62	0.68	0.60	0.55	0.64

The results in Table 3 reveal that technology-driven Assessment is strongly correlated with Teacher ICT Competence ($r = 0.616, p < 0.05$), indicating that digital Assessment practices enhance teachers' ICT skills. Record-Keeping also shows a significant positive relationship with Teacher ICT Competence ($r = 0.510, p < 0.05$), while Instructional Delivery has a weak yet statistically significant correlation with the mediator variable ($r = 0.333, p < 0.05$). The matrix table also indicated that Academic Performance is moderately correlated with Teacher ICT Competence ($r = 0.499, p < 0.05$). This result implies that teachers' technological competence has a positive and significant relationship with students' learning outcomes.

Effect Size Interpretation for Structural Model

Effect size in SEM offers essential insight into the practical impact and real-world relevance of predictor variables. The Cohen's f^2 was used to assess the contribution of each predictor to the variance explained (R^2) in two key endogenous variables: Teacher ICT Competence (TIC) and Academic Performance (AP). Effect sizes (f^2) were interpreted on the basis of benchmarks proposed by Cohen (1988). He stated thus: $f^2 = 0.02$ (small), 0.15 (medium), and 0.35 (large).

Table 4: Effect Size Estimates for Predictors of TIC and AP

Predictor	Outcome	β	T-value	f^2	Effect Size
Assessment (A)	TIC	-0.031	-0.53	0.00	None
Instructional Delivery (ID)	TIC	0.58	7.43	0.38	Large
Record-Keeping (RK)	TIC	0.47	6.81	0.19	Medium
Teacher ICT Competence (TIC)	AP	0.21	2.38	0.06	Small
Assessment (A)	AP	0.25	4.38	0.11	Small-Medium
Instructional Delivery (ID)	AP	0.16	2.07	0.03	Small
Record-Keeping (RK)	AP	0.20	2.91	0.07	Small

Note: β = Standardised coefficient. TIC = Teacher ICT Competence. AP = Academic

The effect size estimates presented in Table 4 reveal that Instructional Delivery (ID), when facilitated through technology, exerts a large effect on Teacher ICT Competence (TIC) ($f^2 = 0.38$). It is the most influential predictor in the model and underscores the central role of digitally mediated instructional practices in strengthening teachers' technological proficiency. Record-Keeping (RK) yielded a medium effect size ($f^2 = 0.19$) on TIC. This implies that record-keeping through digital documentation and the use of technology in performing administrative functions contributes meaningfully to the development of ICT competence among teachers. In contrast, technology-enabled Assessment (A), showed no observable

effect on TIC ($f^2 = 0.00$), which is consistent with its non-significant path coefficient, indicating a limited predictive relevance in this context. With regard to Academic Performance (AP), technology-driven Assessment (A) has the strongest effect ($f^2 = 0.11$). The effect size fell between small and medium level. This implies that technology-driven Assessment has practical importance in enhancing students' learning outcomes. Teacher ICT Competence (TIC) ($f^2 = 0.06$), Record-Keeping (RK) ($f^2 = 0.07$), and Instructional Delivery (ID) ($f^2 = 0.03$) revealed small effect sizes on AP, suggesting thus that their relationships were statistically significant, although their contributions to the explanation of the variance in students' academic performance were modest in practical terms. These findings highlight a differentiated influence of technology integration in teachers' pedagogical practices investigated. Digitally mediated instructional practices and administrative tasks significantly strengthen teacher ICT competence, while technology-driven assessments predominantly enhance students' academic performance, thereby indicating distinct pathways students' academic performance.

Table 5: Fornell-Larcker Discriminant Validity Matrix

Construct	TIC	AP	A	ID	RK
TIC	0.774				
AP	0.574	0.771			
A	0.371	0.462	0.766		
ID	0.697	0.485	0.471	0.836	
RK	0.620	0.451	0.293	0.282	0.657

Table 5 shows that each construct's square root of AVE (diagonal) (in bold) is higher than its correlations with other constructs (off-diagonal). The results confirm that discriminant validity exists between the latent constructs. RK has the weakest inter-construct associations overall, nevertheless, the distinctness of the constructs and the associated indicators is well-established (Fornell & Larcker, 1981).

Table 6: Heterotrait-Monotrait (HTMT) Ratio of Correlations

	TIC	AP	ID	RK
AP	0.656			
ID	0.533	0.601		
RK	0.690	0.533	0.415	
A	0.842	0.670	0.578	0.494

Table 6 presents HTMT matrix of the latent constructs, which indicates that all values fell below the threshold of 0.85, indicating that the ratios among the constructs are within acceptable discriminant validity (Henseler et al., 2015). The highest HTMT value (0.842) is between TIC and A, implying a relatively high but still acceptable similarity. Other pairs showed moderate distinctions among the constructs, affirming convergent validity.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

The findings of this study offers valuable and interesting insights into how technology-based instructional and administrative practices contribute to the development of teachers' ICT competence and students' academic performance. One of the major findings indicates that teachers who engaged in technology-supported instructional delivery demonstrated a high level of ICT competence. This result reinforces the position advanced by Monserate (2018), who argued that classrooms are enriched with multimedia platforms and interactive teaching tools significantly enhanced instructional quality and deepened students' engagement. Abedi (2023) reported that clarity of lessons and student attentiveness was instrumental in improving technology-integrated classrooms, suggesting thus that teachers who adopt digital tools more effectively tend to grow in technological competence over time. This finding, therefore, supports the argument of our model, that it is not merely the presence of digital devices that matters, but

the strategic and consistent use of them in actual teaching processes that builds teacher competence. It also resonates with Gause et al. (2022), who noted that teachers gradually evolve as digital learning facilitators, especially when they are supported with the necessary skills and opportunities to innovate within their instructional spaces.

In the area of record-keeping, this study found a strong connection between technology-based administrative documentation and teacher ICT competence. This aligns with the findings of Igbozuruike and Usman (2019), who reported that digital tools help to reduce the burden of paperwork and increases calculation accuracy. Teachers who used Google Classroom and attendance tracking apps were better able to streamline their workflow and enhance their technical proficiency in the process (Wang & Lu, 2024). Awaji and Solaiman (2022) corroborated the finding, having said that technological solutions such as blockchain-based systems in record management can enhance data accuracy, transparency, and security, thereby improving the overall efficiency and reliability of educational record-keeping processes. This supports the notion that administrative practices can serve as important training grounds for reinforcing digital literacy among teachers, particularly when supported by reliable infrastructure and institutional encouragement.

Interestingly, our study showed no significant relationship between technology-driven assessment and teacher ICT competence. This finding somewhat contradicted the position of Nwonkwo and Ogwunte (2024), who argued that teachers who utilise digital assessment platforms tend to improve their instructional responsiveness and technical capabilities. However, this discrepancy may be explained by the manner in which assessment technologies are implemented, as cautioned by Ukaigwe and Igbozuruike (2019), who observed that teachers may use digital tools only at a surface level, without engaging in the deeper analytical processes that build competence. Similarly, Ventouris et al. (2021) further expressed concern that some digital assessments measure only lower-order thinking skills, which may limit their effectiveness in promoting cognitive engagement for both teachers and learners. Therefore, while digital assessments are intended to improve educational practices, their contribution to teacher ICT development may remain minimal if the tools are inadequate, if their usage lacks depth and training, or if they are not properly aligned with broader pedagogical goals

In terms of how these practices influence academic performance, the findings were more consistent with existing literature. Technology-integrated assessment practices were found to significantly improve academic performance, affirming the positions of Monserate (2018) and Batdi et al. (2018), who both accentuated the instructional value of assessment tools that offer real-time feedback, performance tracking, and personalised guidance. Instructional delivery and record-keeping were also found to be significant predictors of academic outcomes, though at varying degrees of influence. This finding aligns with the findings of Awaji and Solaiman (2022), who reported that digital record-keeping facilitates access to accurate instructional information about students for timely teacher-led intervention, while Adesope and Ezinne (2018) reported that interactive lesson delivery systems foster student-centred learning environments.

Nonetheless, some studies have drawn attention to the challenges that may weaken these positive impacts of technology on overall students' academic performance. Chiukpai et al. (2023) and Gause et al. (2022) noted that irregular power supply, limited internet connectivity, and inadequate teacher training remain key barriers to the successful implementation of technology in schools. These structural constraints often limit the consistency and intensity with which digital tools are applied, thereby affecting their full potential in influencing both teacher competence and academic outcomes. In this light, these findings underscore the critical role of meaningful technology integration in instructional delivery, student assessment, and record-keeping. However, the extent to which these practices influence outcomes depends not only on the availability of technological tools, but also on the teachers' capacity, training, and the institutional structures that support or hinder their effective use. This therefore calls for a more holistic approach to educational technology deployment, in a manner that includes infrastructural

investments, sustained professional development for teachers, and policy alignment to bridge the gap between technological availability and classroom effectiveness.

CONCLUSION

This study employed Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) to examine the relationships between technology-enhanced core pedagogical practices and academic performance, with teacher ICT competence serving as a mediator. Our study used a partially mediated model that demonstrated strong construct reliability, with a clear evidence of convergent and discriminant validity, and acceptable model fit indices. Based on the findings, we conclude that technology-supported instructional delivery and digital record-keeping significantly contribute to improvements in teachers' ICT competence. We also conclude that technology-based assessment showed no measurable impact on teachers' competence development. Student assessment exerted the strongest direct influence on academic performance. In addition, teacher ICT competence served as a strong mediating variable, and effectively facilitates the relationship between technology integration, pedagogical practices and students' academic performance. These conclusions demonstrate the need for full implementation of a technology-supported education system through policy reforms that mandate regular teacher professional development in digital pedagogy, and to ensure adequate infrastructure funding to provide instructional technologies.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were proffered.

1. The Ministry of Education should develop and implement a national framework that integrates ICT competence training into all levels of teacher education and in-service professional development programmes, in a manner that strengthens teachers' capacity to perform their duties using modern technologies
2. School administrators should institutionalise continuous support mechanisms such as regular ICT-focused workshops, peer mentoring, and hands-on digital engagement platforms to enhance teachers' practical proficiency in technology use.
3. Curriculum developers in teacher education institutions, including universities, colleges of education, and specialised institutes, should embed digital assessment literacy into both teaching curricula and instructional guidelines. This should be done in a manner that equips future teachers to effectively deploy digital tools, analyse student performance data, and respond appropriately to learning outcomes.
4. The government should prioritise investments in core ICT infrastructure, especially electricity, internet access, and digital learning systems to sustain consistent and scalable technology adoption in schools.

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